

Hamilton-Jacobi with Continuity Equation Approaches to Deriving the Schrodinger Equation And the Role of Averaging

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 22, 2024

There are numerous papers in the literature which use the classical Hamilton-Jacobi equation together with the continuity equation for density as well as some assumptions to obtain the Schrodinger equation. Here we focus on the approach of (1) (from 2024) and, in particular, focus on the averaging which is implicitly assumed for both a bound particle and free one in this approach. We argue that once the notion of the kind of averaging process that is used is apparent, one may apply this averaging (which essentially means not following the particle in time) to obtain a free particle wavefunction as well as an ensemble of free particles needed to create a bound state without using the Hamilton-Jacobi or continuity equations.

Hamilton-Jacobi with Continuity Equation Approach of (1)

We very briefly outline the approach of (1). Classically, it is argued that one has:

Hamilton-Jacobi equation: $\frac{dS}{dt} + \text{grad } S \cdot \text{grad } S + V = 0$ ((1)) and

Continuity Equation $\frac{dD}{dt} + (1/m) \text{grad} \cdot (D \text{grad} S) = 0$ ((2))

Here $D(x,t)$ is density and S , action. (1) points out that $\text{grad } S = p$, the ensemble average. Then (1) becomes the usual conservation of energy equation.

(1) notes that both the Hamilton-Jacobi and continuity equations may be obtained through variation of:

$\int D \left(\frac{dS}{dt} + \text{grad } S \cdot \text{grad } S + V \right) dx dy dz dt$ ((3))

(The H-J equation is obtained by varying D and the continuity, by varying S (i.e. using integration by parts.)

(1) keeps the notion of obtaining equations through variation, but adds an extra term for the quantum case, namely: $\int dx dy dz dt \frac{\hbar}{4m} \frac{1}{D} \text{grad } D \cdot \text{grad } D$ ((4))

We do not go through the arguments presented in (1) used to justify the approach, but rather examine the results for two cases:

- (A) a free particle and
- (B) a bound particle.

We find that in order to make sense of the results of (1), one must consider S as being an averaged quantity in the sense that one does not follow a particle in time. The ultimate results of (1) are:

$$dS/dt \text{ partial} + 1/2m \text{ grad}D \text{ dot grad}S + V - \hbar(\hbar)/2m (1/\text{sqrt}(D) \text{ grad dot grad sqrt}(D)) \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{with } W = \text{wavefunction} = \text{sqrt}(D) \exp(iS) \quad ((6))$$

Bound Case

A bound particle moves in a localized region of space (here $V(x)$) and so average momentum is 0. If one were to consider the averaged bound particle as one with average energy and average momentum=0, then:

$$E_{ave} = E \text{ (same at each } x) \quad \text{and } p_{ave} = 0 \quad ((7))$$

One may write the relativistic or nonrelativistic action for a particle with energy E and $p=0$ as:

$$S = -Et + px - V = -Et \quad ((8)) \text{ (free particle type action)}$$

((6)), however, is a special averaged quantity.

In such a case, in order to make ((5)) hold for a bound state: $dS/dt \text{ partial} = -E$ and $\text{grad } S = 0$. Earlier $\text{grad}S = p(x)$, but now an averaged $\text{grad}S$ is being used. It is as if one does not follow the particle in time. We thus suggest that caution must be used in interpreting S and even D in Hamilton Jacobi approaches used to obtain the Schrodinger equation. For the bound case, it is S which is treated in an average way, but for a free particle, it is D , as we argue in the next section.

Averaging and the Free Particle

The continuity equation for a free particle means that:

$$D(x,t) = \text{delta function} [x - (x_0 + vt)] \quad ((9))$$

Then ((2)) is satisfied. For a free particle: $S = -Et + px$ (both relativistically and nonrelativistically with $v=x/t$).

In order for ((5)) to be satisfied, one must use $D = \text{constant}$, i.e. $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx)$ and not ((9)), the classical density. How are $D = \text{constant}$ and ((2)) related? ((2)) follows the particle in time. If one does not follow the particle in time, then it has the same probability (i.e. the peak of the delta function) at each x . This leads to $P(x) = 1/L$ in a length region L .

Formally, the result of one (1) states that: $W = \text{sqrt}(D) \exp(iS)$. For $S = -Et + px$ and using the known quantum result that $W = \exp(-iEt + ipx) / \text{sqrt}(L)$, then D must be a constant which is not ((2)), but an averaged quantity, i.e. the notion of motion in time has been removed.

Thus, we argue that the key feature in the Hamilton-Jacobi / continuity approaches is to the special averaging which occurs, i.e. the removal of the notion of following a particle in time.

Using Averaging Alone to Determine the Quantum Free Particle Wavefunction

We examine this averaging notion in more detail. If a particle moves in time with constant p , and one removes time, i.e. does not follow the particle in time, then:

$$P(x)dx = 1/L dx \quad ((10))$$

As argued in previous notes, this is classically the probability for finding a stationary object at x in classical probability. A stationary object, however, is equivalent to a $p, -p$ pair, so is related to an AND situation:

$$P(x) = 1/L = P_d(px) P_d(-px) \text{ or } P_d(px) = \exp(ipx) \text{ as a solution} \quad ((11))$$

Thus, we argue that the results of (1) may be obtained by considering the type of averaging which is implied. In such a case, the time independent Schrodinger equation follows from average conservation of energy using: $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$. One may replace EW with $-\hbar d/dt \text{ partial } \exp(-iEt)$ to obtain the time dependent result.

We thus suggest that quantum mechanics follows from viewing a classical situation in a special way, i.e. removing time, and trying to describe probability in such a case. We suggest that one may immediately obtain $\exp(ipx)$ if one considers this viewpoint and that the averaging procedure used in Hamilton-Jacobi / continuity type approaches could be missed.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that variational approaches which use the classical Hamilton-Jacobi and continuity equations and add an extra term, actually use special average values of S (action) and $D(x,t)$, density. In particular, for a bound system, $S = -Et + px$ with $p=0$ because on average the particle does not move and for a free particle, $D(x,t)$ is no longer $\delta(x - (x_0 + vt))$, but rather $1/L$.

If one keeps this special averaging in mind, we argue that one might apply it a priori without using the Hamilton-Jacobi or continuity equations. In particular, if one has a free particle in a region $1/L$ and does not follow it in time, then $P(x)dx = 1/L dx$. This, however, is the classical probability for stationary objects distributed in x . We argue that this should be equivalent to a $-p, p$ pair and so $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx)$ is a way to obtain $1/L$. One may then form $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and use average conservation of energy to obtain the time-independent Schrodinger equation. To obtain the time-dependent one, one may use $W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt) W(x)$ and $EW \rightarrow \hbar d/dt \text{ partial } W$.

References.

1. Jang, J. Quantum Mechanics Based on Information Metrics for Vacuum Fluctuations (2024)
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/b02a56dac5362fbeb3b4554fd485a46dcd36b90b>